

MESOSCALE CLIMATE MODELING ABOVE A METHANE LAKE ON TITAN. A. Chatain^{1,2}, S.C.R. Rafkin², A. Soto² and R. Hueso¹, ¹Departamento de Física Aplicada I, ETS Ingenieros, Universidad del País Vasco, Alameda Urquijo s/n, 48013 Bilbao, Spain, ²Department of Space Studies, Southwest Research Institute, 1050 Walnut Street, Suite 300, Boulder, CO, USA (audrey.chatain@boulder.swri.edu).

Introduction: Titan is the only known place beyond the Earth to have lakes and seas. On Earth, we know that liquid surfaces are constantly subject to evaporation and that they strongly modify the local climate and drive the planet water cycle. Then, what climate could we expect on Titan in the environment of methane lakes? And how their evaporation does control the methane cycle?

We investigate this using mesoscale climate modeling. Currently there are no advanced mesoscale or large eddy simulation models of Titan. The first models came out only very recently (by Rafkin & Soto [1], Lavelly et al [2] and Spiga et al [3]). Each focus on a specific point (methane evaporation, topography, turbulence), but none of them handles all of the key processes yet.

Development of the model: We use the mtWRF 2D model first described in [1], which simulates the effect of a methane lake on the local climate. The mtWRF model previously lacked the implementation of diurnally varying solar insolation and radiative transfer through the atmosphere. However, previous results in [1] suggested that these effects could be important on the lake-induced wind circulation even though solar forcing is small on Titan's surface.

We thus added a simple gray radiative transfer scheme to the model. It takes into account solar radiation scattering through the atmosphere [4] and reflection at the surface, as well as IR radiation emission and absorption in the atmosphere and at the surface [5].

Results on winds: development of a sea breeze with diurnal variations: Results with or without radiative transfer show the same initial development. The simulations start with a strong evaporation of the lake accompanied by a rising moist plume and a land breeze circulation (wind from land to sea at the surface). Due to evaporation, the lake cools down and after a few hours, a sea breeze forms, and then extends well outside the limits of the lake (see Fig. 1).

The simulation with radiative transfer shows the formation of the strongest winds during daytime at the lake shores (because of an increase of the temperature difference between the quickly warming land and the slowly warming lake). At the shores, a clear diurnal variation is observed, with an averaged value and a maximum value higher than in the case without radiative transfer (see Fig. 2a-b).

Fig. 1: Formation of an initial plume and land breeze then replaced by a strong sea breeze, extending over the land.

Results on methane vapor: Methane evaporation is the strongest at the center of the lake on the first day of simulation, but after a few days, it mainly comes from the sides of the lake (see Fig. 2c), where winds are the strongest. As with the wind data, a clear diurnal frequency is observed: methane evaporation happens mainly in the afternoons. Methane vapor is then spread over land by the winds.

Results on surface temperature: The diurnally-varying insolation induces an oscillation in the land and lake surface temperatures (see Fig. 3). The lake is slower to react to insolation variations because of the increase of evaporation during the day, which has a cooling effect opposite to the solar warming. The side parts of the lake stabilize at a lower temperature than the center because it undergoes stronger evaporation. Both values are higher than the lake surface temperature obtained in the simulation without radiative transfer.

Conclusion: Although small, the solar insolation at Titan's surface and its diurnal variation has a significant impact on the evaporation of methane lakes. It influences the local wind circulation with strong diurnal variations in the sea breeze intensity. Resulting mean lake surface temperature is increased by a few Kelvins compared to the case without radiative transfer.

Short term perspectives: We now start to investigate simulations performed at different seasons and latitudes. This will help to explain why lakes are mainly observed at the north pole on Titan, and what are the effects of seasons on lake evaporation and the local atmospheric circulation.

Fig. 2: Horizontal wind over lake and land as a function of time in the case (a) without radiative transfer (RT), and (b) with RT. (c) Methane vapor near the surface in the simulation with RT.

Fig. 3: Surface temperature at different positions on the lake and the land, obtained for the 2 simulations.

Perspectives for Dragonfly: The Dragonfly mission will explore Titan’s surface by 2034 with a dual-quadcopter [6]. It will fly once every Titan day (16 Earth days) to another exploration site a few kilometers away. No orbiter will accompany the rotorcraft lander and Dragonfly will have to rely on climate models to prepare its operations. The dense 1.5-bar atmosphere on Titan implies that even small winds can be powerful and need to be taken into account during the Dragonfly mission. Strong winds can be caused by evaporative effects, which happen on lakes, but which could also happen on wetlands, possibly present near the Dragonfly landing site [7]. The next step of our study will then be to model evaporation above wetlands.

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